

MELKERSSON CONDITION AND SERRE SUBCATEGORIES

Rasul Rasuli¹ and Sebar Ghaderi^{2*}

¹ Department of Mathematics, Payame Noor University(PNU), P. O. Box 19395-4697, Tehran, Iran

^{2*} Department of Mathematics, Payame Noor University(PNU), P. O. Box 19395-4697, Tehran, Iran

Abstract

Let R be a noetherain ring, a be an ideal of R , M and N R -modules. Let δ be a Serre subcategory of the category of R -module . We define δ - $\dim(M)$ and δ - $\dim(M, N)$. We fine some conditions under which $H_a^i(M)$ and $H_a^i(M, N)$ belong δ for all $i \geq 0$.

Keywords: Dimension theory, Serre subcategory, Melkersson condition, Local cohomology.

2000 AMS Classification: 13C15, 13C60, 13D45.

1. INTRODUCTION

Throughout R is a commutative noetherian ring. As a general reference to homological and commutative algebra we use [1]. Recall that a class of R -modules is a serre subcategory of the category of R -modules when it is closed under taking submodules, quotients and extensions. Always, δ stands for a serre subcategory of the category of R -modules. Hence, if $L \rightarrow M \rightarrow N$ is an exact sequence of the category of R -modules and R -homomorphisms such that both end terms belong to δ , then M is also belong to δ . Note that the following subcategories are examples of serre subcategory of the category of the R -modules: finite R -modules; coatomic R -modules [14]; minimax R -modules [15] and trivially the zero R -modules. Generalized local cohomology was intrduced by Grothendieck [10]. They are defined as the right derived functors of the left exact functor $\Gamma_a(\text{Hom}_R(M, -))$. Here M is a finite R -modules. They can also be computed as $H_a^i(M, N) \cong \lim_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \text{Ext}_R^i(M/a^n M, N)$ where N is an arbitrary R -modules. If $0 \rightarrow L \rightarrow P \rightarrow Q \rightarrow 0$ is an exact sequence of R -modules, then there are long exact sequence

$$0 \rightarrow H_a^0(M, L) \rightarrow H_a^0(M, P) \rightarrow H_a^0(M, Q) \rightarrow \dots$$

$$H_a^n(M, L) \rightarrow H_a^n(M, P) \rightarrow H_a^n(M, Q) \rightarrow \dots$$

It is well-known that the Generalized local cohomology and ordinary local cohomology modules are not in Serre class of the category of R -modules in general. This notion has been studied by several authors; see, for example [1, 2, 4, 5] and [12]. Our objective in this paper is to define δ - $\dim(M)$ and δ - $\dim(M, N)$ such that we characterize the membership of $H_a^i(M)$ and $H_a^i(M, N)$ to δ for all $i \geq 0$. Recall that if M be an R -module and a an ideal of R , the height of a on M and the Krull dimension of M with respect to δ are defined as $\delta ht_M(a) := \inf\{ht_M(q) | q \in \delta - \text{supp}(M) \cap V(a)\}$ and $\delta - \dim(M) := \sup\{ht_M(q) | q \in \delta - \text{supp}(M)\}$ respectively.

2. SOME RESULTS IN LOCAL COHOMOLOGY AND SERRE SUBCATEGORY

The following Lemma and remark characterize membership of M to δ .

Lemma 2.1. Let $\delta \neq 0$ be a Serre subcategory of the category of R -modules. If $\delta - \dim(M) = 0$ and M be a finite R -module then $M \in \delta$.

Proof. Let M is not in δ , so by [4, Lemma 2.1], R/\mathfrak{p} is not in δ , for some $\mathfrak{p} \in \text{Supp}_R(M)$ and we have $\mathfrak{p} \in \delta - \text{Supp}_R(M)$ such that $ht_M(\mathfrak{p}) \neq 0$, consequently $\delta - \dim(M) \neq 0$ which is a contradiction.

Remark 2.2. Let $M \neq 0$ be a finite R -module. If $H_a^i(M) \in \delta$ then by [4, Lemma 2.1], $R/\mathfrak{p} \in \delta$ such that $\mathfrak{p} \in H_a^i(M) \subset \text{Supp}_R(M) \cap V(a)$, so $\mathfrak{p} \in \text{Supp}_R(M)$ and $M \in \delta$.

Definition 2.3. (See [6, Definition 2.2.1]) Let M be an R -module. The generalized ideal transform functor with respect to an ideal a of R is defined by $D_a(M, 0) = \lim_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \rightarrow \text{Hom}_R(a^n M, 0)$. Let $R^i D_a(M, 0)$ denote the i -th right derived functor of $D_a(M, 0)$. One can check easily that there is a natural isomorphism $R^i D_a(M, 0) \cong \lim_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \rightarrow \text{Ext}_R^i(a^n M, 0)$.

Proposition 2.4. Let M be an R -module such that $\text{Ext}_R^i(R/a, M) \in \delta$. If $\text{Ext}_R^i(R/a, \Gamma_a(M)) \in \delta$, then $\text{Hom}_R(R/a, H_a^i(M)) \in \delta$.

Proof. The exact sequence $0 \rightarrow \Gamma_a(M) \rightarrow M \rightarrow M/\Gamma_a(M) \rightarrow 0$ induces the long exact sequence

$$\cdots \text{Ext}_R^i(R/a, M) \rightarrow \text{Ext}_R^1(R/a, M/\Gamma_a(M)) \rightarrow \text{Ext}_R^2(R/a, \Gamma_a(M)) \rightarrow \cdots$$

So $\text{Ext}_R^1(R/a, M/\Gamma_a(M)) \in \delta$. We know that $\text{Hom}_R(R/a, D_a(M)) \cong (0 : D_a(M)(M)) \subseteq \Gamma_a(D_a(M)) = 0$ so $\text{Hom}_R(R/a, D_a(M)) \in \delta$.

The exact sequence $0 \rightarrow M/\Gamma_a(M) \rightarrow D_a(M) \rightarrow H_a^1(M) \rightarrow 0$

induce the long exact sequence

$$\cdots \rightarrow \text{Hom}_R(R/a, D_a(M)) \rightarrow \text{Hom}_R(R/a, H_a^1(M)) \rightarrow \text{Ext}_R^1(R/a, M/\Gamma_a(M)) \rightarrow \cdots$$

So $\text{Hom}_R(R/a, H_a^1(M)) \in \delta$.

In [3], M. Aghapournahr and L. Melkersson gave the following condition on serre subcategory or R-modules.

Definition 2.5. Let δ be a serre subcategory of the category of R-modules. We say that δ satisfies the condition: (C_α) if $M = \Gamma_\alpha(M)$ and if $0 : M_\alpha$ is in δ then M is in δ .

Example 2.6. The class of zero modules and artinian R-modules satisfy the condition C_α .

The following easy Lemma is useful in proof of the next theorem and we lift it to the reader.

Lemma 2.7. Let a be an ideal of R, let δ be a serre subcategory; and let $M \in \delta$. Then $\text{Ext}_R^i(R/a, M) \in \delta$ for each $i \geq 0$.

The following Theorem is the main result of this section. In fact we generalize the Vanishing Theory of Grothendieck.

Theorem 2.8. Let δ be a serre subcategory of the category of R-modules. If δ satisfies the condition C_α , then $H_a^i(M) \in \delta$ for all $i > \delta - \dim M$.

Proof. When $\delta - \dim(M) = -1$, there is nothing to prove, as when $M = 0$. The result is also clear if $a = R$, as then Γ_α is the zero functor. We therefor suppose henceforth in this proof that $M \neq 0$ and $a \subseteq \mathfrak{m}$. We argue by induction on $\delta - \dim(M)$. Let $\delta - \dim(M) = 0$. Since for each $i \geq 0$, the local cohomology functor H_a^i commutes with direct limit, and M can be viewed as the direct of its finitely generated submodules, it is sufficient for us to prove that $H_a^i(M) \in \delta$ whenever M is a finitely generated R-module, so by Lemma 2.1 and Lemma 2.7 $H_a^i(M) \in \delta$ for all $i > \delta - \dim M$. Now suppose, inductively, that $\delta - \dim M = n$ and the result has been proved for all R-modules of $\delta - \dim M$ smaller than $n > 0$. It follows

that $H_a^i(M) \cong H_a^i(M/\Gamma_\alpha(M))$ for all $i > 0$. Also, $M/\Gamma_\alpha(M)$ is an a -torsion-free R -module. Then, in view of, the ideal a contains an element x which is M -regular. The exact sequence

$$0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow M \rightarrow M/xM \rightarrow 0$$

induce a long exact sequence

$$\dots \rightarrow H_a^{i-1}(M/xM) \rightarrow H_a^i(M) \rightarrow H_a^i(M) \rightarrow \dots$$

Since $\delta - \dim(M/xM) \leq (\delta - \dim(M)) - (\delta - \text{ht}_R(M)) = n - 1$, by induction hypothesis $H_a^{i-1}(M/xM) \in \delta$ and by the above exact sequence, we have $(0 : H_a^i(M)x) \in \delta$ so $H_a^i(M) \in \delta$ for all $i > \delta - \dim(M)$.

Remark 2.9. In Theorem 2.8 if δ satisfies the condition C_a , then $\delta - \dim(M) = \sup\{i | H_a^i(M) \in \delta\}$ and if $L \rightarrow M \rightarrow N$ be an exact sequence of finite R -modules, then $\delta - \dim(M) = \max\{\delta - \dim(N), \delta - \dim(L)\}$.

Definition 2.10. Let δ be a serre subcategory of the R -modules and let M be a module over the noetherain ring R . Following [3] an element x of R is called δ -regular on M if module $o: Mx$ is in δ . A sequence x_1, \dots, x_n is an δ -sequence on M if x_j is δ -regular on $M / (x_1, \dots, x_{j-1})M$ for $j = 0, 1, \dots, n$. Also if M be a finite module such that M / aM is not in δ , where δ satisfies the condition C_a , then we denote the common length of all maximal δ -regular on M in a by $\delta - \text{depth}_a(M)$.

Example 2.11. Let δ be the class of zero modules, so $\delta - \text{depth}_a(M)$. Will be the same an ordinary $\text{depth}_a(M)$.

Corollary 2.12. Let M be a finite module and let a be an ideal of R such that M / aM is not in δ , if δ be a serre subcategory of the category of R -modules, the satisfies the condition C_a , then any integer I for which $H_a^i(M)$ is not in δ much satisfies $\delta - \text{depth}_a(M) \leq i \leq \delta - \dim(M)$.

Proof. Use Theorem 2.8 and [3, Theorem 2. 18].

Definition 2.13. (See[3, Definition 3.5]) Let δ be a serre subcategory of the category of R -module. For each R -module M , set $\text{ch}_g(a, M) = \sup\{i | H_a^i(M) \in \delta\}$ which is called δ -cohomological dimension of M with respect to a . The δ -cohomological dimension of a is $\text{ch}_g(a) = \sup\{\text{ch}_g(a, M)\}$ for all R -module M .

Example 2.14. Let $\delta = \{0\}$, then $\text{ch}_g(a, M) = \text{cd}(a, M)$, and if δ , be the class of artinian modules, then $\text{ch}_g(a, M) = \text{q}(a, M)$ as in [11] and [9].

Proposition 2.15. Let a be an ideal of R . Then $\text{ch}_g(a, R) = \text{ch}_g(a)$.

Proof. Set $d = \text{ch}_g(a)$. Since R is noetherian so a can be generated by t elements. Then by [6, Theorem 3.3.1] $H_a^i(M) \in \delta$ for all $i > t$, and d will be finite. Thus, $H_a^n(M) \in \delta$ for all $n \geq d + 1$, and there is an R -module M with $H_a^n(M)$ is not in δ . Pick a surjective homomorphism $F \rightarrow M$, with F a free R -module, and complete to an exact sequence $0 \rightarrow K \rightarrow F \rightarrow M \rightarrow 0$. From the resulting long exact sequence, one obtain an exact sequence $H_a^d(K) \rightarrow H_a^d(F) \rightarrow H_a^d(M) \rightarrow H_a^{d+1}(K)$. We conclude that $H_a^d(F)$ is not in δ , and so $H_a^d(R) \in \delta$.

The following Theorem shows the relationship between $\text{ch}_g(M)$ and $\delta - \dim(M)$.

Theorem 2.16. Let δ be a Serre subcategory of the category of R -modules. If δ satisfies the condition C_a , then $\text{ch}_g(a, M) \leq \delta - \dim(M)$.

Proof. When $\text{ch}_g(a, M) = -\infty$ or $\delta - \dim(M) = \infty$, there is nothing to prove. If $\delta - \dim(M) = 0$, then by Theorem we have $\text{ch}_g(a, M) = 0$. Now suppose, inductively, that $\delta - \dim(M) = d$ such that $d > 0$ and the result has been proved for all R -modules of δ -dimensions smaller than n . In fact we prove $H_a^i(M) \in \delta$ for all $i > n$. Let $L = M/\Gamma_a(M)$, then $l = \delta - \dim(L) \leq \delta - \dim(M) = n$, and it is sufficient for us to prove $H_a^i(L) \in \delta$ for all $i > l$.

Since $\Gamma_a(L) = 0$, we have $\Gamma_a(M) = 0$ and the ideal a contains an element x which is M -regular. The exact sequence $0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow M \rightarrow M/xM \rightarrow 0$ induce a long exact sequence $H_a^{i-1}(M/xM) \rightarrow H_a^i(M) \rightarrow H_a^i(M)$. Since $\delta - \dim(M/xM) < n - 1$, it follows from the hypothesis, $H_a^{i-1}(M/xM) \in \delta$. Also, by above exact sequence and the condition C_a , $(0 :_{H_a^i(M)} x) \in \delta$, so $H_a^i(M) \in \delta$ for all $i > n$.

Corollary 2.17. Let δ be a Serre subcategory of the category of R -modules. If δ satisfies the condition C_a , then $\text{cd}_g(m) \leq \delta - \dim(R)$.

Proposition 2.18. Let δ be a Serre subcategory of the category of R -modules. If δ satisfies the condition C_a . If N be submodule of M , then $\delta - \dim(N) \leq \delta - \dim(M)$, and $\delta - \dim(M/N) \leq \delta - \dim(M)$.

Proof. Let $\delta - \dim(M) < d$. By exact sequence $0 \rightarrow N \rightarrow M \rightarrow M/N \rightarrow 0$,

We would have the long exact sequence

$$\dots \rightarrow H_a^d(N) \rightarrow H_a^d(M) \rightarrow H_a^d\left(\frac{M}{N}\right) \rightarrow H_a^{d+1}(N) \rightarrow \dots$$

So from Remark 2.9, $H_a^d(N) \in \delta$, and $H_a^d(M/N) \in \delta$.

3. A STUDY OF GENERALIZED LOCAL COHOMOLOGY UNDER CONDITION C_a

Lemma 3.1. (See [8, Lemma 2.2]) Let M be an R -module. For any R -module N , there is an exact sequence,

$$0 \rightarrow H_a^0(M, N) \rightarrow \text{Hom}_R(M, N) \rightarrow D_a(M, N) \rightarrow H_a^1(M, N) \rightarrow \dots \\ \rightarrow H_a^i(M, N) \rightarrow \text{Ext}_R^i(M, N) \rightarrow R^i D_a(M, N) \rightarrow H_a^{i+1}(M, N) \rightarrow \dots,$$

moreover, if M has finite projective dimension, then there is a natural isomorphism $H_a^{1+i}(M, N) \cong R^i D_a(M, N)$ for all $i \geq \text{pd}M + 1$.

Proposition 3.2. Let a, b be ideals of ring R_i such that $a \subseteq b$. Let $\text{Ext}_R^1(R/b, \text{Hom}_R(M, N)) \in \delta$, such that $\text{Ext}_R^2(R/a, H_a^0(M, N)) \in \delta$. If $\text{Ext}_R^1(M, N) = 0$, then $\text{Hom}_R(R/b, H_a^1(M, N)) \in \delta$.

Proof. The exact sequence

$$0 \rightarrow H_a^0(M, N) \rightarrow \text{Hom}_R(M, N) \rightarrow \text{Hom}_R(M, N)/H_a^0(M, N) \rightarrow 0$$

induce the long exact sequence

$$\dots \rightarrow \text{Ext}_R^1(R/b, \text{Hom}_R(M, N)) \rightarrow \text{Ext}_R^1(R/b, \text{Hom}_R(M, N)/H_a^0(M, N)) \rightarrow \text{Ext}_R^2(R/b, H_a^0(M, N)) \dots,$$

then $\text{Ext}_R^1(R/b, \text{Hom}_R(M, N)/H_a^0(M, N)) \in \delta$. By Lemma 3.1, and $\text{Ext}_R^1(M, N) = 0$, we have the exact sequence

$$0 \rightarrow \text{Hom}_R(M, N)/H_a^0(M, N) \rightarrow D_a(M, N) \rightarrow H_a^1(M, N) \rightarrow 0$$

and

$$\dots \rightarrow \text{Hom}_R(R/b, D_a(M, N)) \rightarrow \text{Hom}_R(R/b, H_a^1(M, N)) \rightarrow \text{Ext}_R^1(R/b, \text{Hom}_R(M, N)/H_a^0(M, N)) \rightarrow \dots.$$

Since $\text{Hom}_R(R/b, D_a(M, N)) \cong (0 :_{D_a(M, N)} b) \subseteq \Gamma_a(D_a(M, N)) = 0$, so $\text{Hom}_R(R/b, D_a(M, N)) \in \delta$, and $\text{Hom}_R(R/b, H_a^1(M, N)) \in \delta$.

Proposition 3.3. Let $\text{Ext}_R^i(R/a, n) \in \delta$ for all $0 \leq i \leq t$ if $H_a^i(M, N) \in \delta$ for all $0 \leq i \leq t$ then $\text{Hom}_R(R/a, H_a^i(M, N)) \in \delta$.

Proof. We use induction on t . By Lemma 2.7 for $t = 0$, proof is clear. The exact sequence

$$0 \rightarrow \text{Hom}_a^0(M, N) \text{Hom}_R(M, N) \rightarrow \text{Hom}_R(M, N)/H_a^0(M, N) \rightarrow 0,$$

induce a long exact sequence

$$0 \rightarrow \text{Hom}_R(R/a, H_a^0(M, N)) \rightarrow \text{Hom}_R(R/a, \text{Hom}_a(M, N)) \rightarrow \dots$$

Suppose that $t > 0$ and that the result has been proved for smaller values of t . It follows [6, corollary 2.1.7] that $H_a^i(N) \cong H_a^i(N/\Gamma_a(N))$ for all $i > 0$ so $\Gamma_a(N) = 0$. Let $E_R(N)$ be an injective envelope of N , and $L =$

$E_R(N)/N$ so $0 \rightarrow N \rightarrow E_R(N) \rightarrow L \rightarrow 0$ will be exact, and we have: $\Gamma_a(E_R(M)) = 0, \text{Hom}_R(R/a, E_R(M)) = 0, H_a^0(M, E_R(N)) = 0$. Therefore we have for all $i \geq 0$: $\text{Ext}_R^{i+1}\left(\frac{R}{a}, L\right) \cong \text{Ext}_R^{i+1}\left(\frac{R}{a}, N\right), H_a^i(M, L) \cong H_a^{i+1}(M, N), H_a^i(L) \cong H_a^{i+1}(N)$. The inductive step will be completed from the inductive hypothesis about L and this fact that $\text{Hom}_R(R/a, H_a^i(M, N)) \cong \text{Hom}_R(R/a, H_a^{i-1}(M, L))$.

Definition 3.4. Let δ be a Serre subcategory of the category of R -modules. For two R -modules M and N set $\delta - \dim(M, N) = \sup\{i \mid H_a^i(M, N) \in \delta\}$ which is called δ -generalized cohomological dimension of M and N with respect to a .

Theorem 3.5. If $x \in a$ be a regular element on N . Then $\delta - \dim(M, N/xN) \leq \delta - \dim(M, N)$.

Proof. Let $\delta - \dim(M, N) = n$. Then $H_a^i(M, N) \in \delta$ for all $i \geq n$. The exact sequence $0 \rightarrow N \rightarrow N \rightarrow N/xN \rightarrow 0$ implies the following long exact sequence of generalized local cohomology modules.

$$H_a^{n+1}(M, N) \rightarrow H_a^{n+1}(M, N/xN) \rightarrow H_a^{n+2}(M, N/xN) \rightarrow \dots$$

We get $H_a^{n+1}(M, N/xN) \in \delta$ and so $\delta - \dim(M, N/xN) \leq n$.

The following Proposition is a generalization of [13, Proposition 2.4].

Proposition 3.6. Let (R, m) be a local ring such that $H_a^i(M, N) \in \delta$ for all $i < n$, and δ satisfies the condition C_a , then $\Gamma_m(H_a^n(M, N)) \in \delta$.

Proof. It follows from 3.3 that $\text{Hom}_R(R/a, H_a^n(M, N)) \in \delta$. Since $\Gamma_m(\text{Hom}_R(R/a, H_a^n(M, N)))$ is subset of $\text{Hom}_R(R/a, H_a^n(M, N))$ then $\Gamma_m(\text{Hom}_R(R/a, H_a^n(M, N))) \in \delta$.

By the isomorphism $\Gamma_m(0_{H_a^n(M, N)} a) \cong (0_{\Gamma_m(H_a^n(M, N))} a)$ and condition C_a , $\Gamma_m(H_a^n(M, N)) \in \delta$.

4. Open Problem

Recall that A fuzzy subset of a set X , we mean a function from X into $[0,1]$.

A t -norm T is a function $T: [0,1] \times [0,1] \rightarrow [0,1]$ having the following four properties:

- (1) $T(x, 1) = x$,
- (2) $T(x, y) \leq T(x, z)$ if $y \leq z$,
- (3) $T(x, y) = T(y, x)$,
- (4) $T(x, T(y, z)) = T(T(x, y), z)$, for all $x, y, z \in [0,1]$.

An s -norm S is a function $S : [0,1] \times [0,1] \rightarrow [0,1]$ having the following four properties:

- (1) $S(x, 0) = x$,
- (2) $S(x, y) \leq S(x, z)$ if $y \leq z$,
- (3) $S(x, y) = S(y, x)$,
- (4) $S(x, S(y, z)) = S(S(x, y), z)$, for all $x, y, z \in [0,1]$.

Now one can define and consider fuzzy $\delta - \dim(\mathbf{M})$, fuzzy $\delta - \dim(\mathbf{M}, \mathbf{N})$, fuzzy $H_a^i(\mathbf{M})$ and fuzzy $H_a^i(\mathbf{M}, \mathbf{N})$ for all $i \geq 0$, with respect to norms as First author investigated [12-23]. This can be an open problem for readers in the future.

Acknowledgment. The authors would like to be thankful to the anonymous reviewers for their valuable suggestions.

REFERENCE

- [1] M. Aghapournahr, *Upper bounds for finiteness of generalized local cohomology modules*, *Journal of Algebraic System*, 1(1) (2013) 1-9.
- [2] M. Aghapournahr; A.J. Taherizadeh, and A. Vahidi, *Extension function of local cohomology modules*, *arXiv:0903.2093v1[math.A.C]*, 12 Mar 2009.
- [3] M. Aghapournahr; L. Melkersson, *Local cohomology and Serre subcategory*, *J. Algebra*, 320(2008), 1275-1287.
- [4] M. Asgharzadeh and M. Tousi, *Cohen-Macaulayness with respect to Serre classes*, *Illinois.J.Math*, 53(2009), no. 1, 67-85.
- [5] M. Asgharzadeh and M. Tousi, *A Unified approach to local cohomology modules using serre classes* *arXivmath/0712.3875v2 [math.AC]*, 8 Apr 2008.
- [6] M. Brodmann and R. Y. Sharp, *Local cohomology: an algebraic introduction with geometric applications*, *Cambridge Studies in Advanced Mathematics* 60, Cambridge University Press(1998).
- [7] F. Dehghani-Zadeh, *On the finiteness properties of generalized local cohomology modules*, *International Electronic Journal of Algebra* 10(2011),113-122.
- [8] K. Divaani-aazar and R. Saezede, *Cofiniteness of generalized local cohomology modules*, *arXiv:04081163v1[math.AC]*, 12 Aug 2004.
- [9] M. T. Dibaei and S. Yassemi, *Associated primes and cofiniteness of local cohomology modules*, *Manuscripta math* 117(2005),199-205.
- [10] A. Grothendieck, *Cohomology local des faisceaux coherents et theoremes de lefschitz locaux et globaux (SGA 2)*, North-Holland, Amsterdam, 1968.
- [11] R. Hartshorne, *Cohomological dimension of algebraic varieties*, *Ann. of Math.* 88(1968),403-450
- [12] R. Rasuli, *serre subcategory in abelian category*, *International Journal of Algebra*, 7(12) (2013), 549-557.

- [13] R. Rasuli, Norms Over Intuitionistic Fuzzy Subgroups on Direct Product of Groups, *Commun. Combin., Cryptogr. Computer Sci.*, **1(2023)**, 39-54.
- [14] R. Rasuli, T-Fuzzy subalgebras of BCI-algebras, *Int. J. Open Problems Compt. Math.*, **16(1)(2023)**, 55-72.
- [15] R. Rasuli, Norms over Q -intuitionistic fuzzy subgroups of a group, *Notes on Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets*, **29(1)(2023)**, 30-45.
- [16] R. Rasuli, Fuzzy ideals of BCI-algebras with respect to t -norm, *Mathematical Analysis and its Contemporary Applications*, **5(5)(2023)**, 30-50.
- [17] R. Rasuli, Intuitionistic fuzzy complex subgroups with respect to norms(T and S), *Journal of Fuzzy Extention and Application*, **4(2)(2023)**, 92-114.
- [18] R. Rasuli, Normality and translation of $IFS(G \times Q)$ under norms, *Notes on Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets*, **29(2)(2023)**, 114-132.
- [19] R. Rasuli, Normalization, commutativity and centralization of $TFSM(G)$, *Journal of Discrete Mathematical Sciences Cryptography*, **26(4)(2023)**, 1027-1050.
- [20] R. Rasuli, Intuitionistic fuzzy G -modules with respect to norms (T and S), *Notes on Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets*, **29(3)(2023)**, 277-291.
- [21] R. Rasuli, Complex fuzzy lie subalgebras and complex fuzzy ideals under t -norms, *Journal of Fuzzy Extention and Application*, **4(3)(2023)**, 173-187.
- [22] R. Rasuli, Anti fuzzy B -subalgebras under S -norms, *Commun. Combin., Cryptogr. Computer Sci.*, **1(2023)**, 61-74.
- [23] R. Rasuli, Complex intuitionistic fuzzy Lie subalgebras under norms, *Notes on Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets*, **31(1)(2025)**, 15-28.
- [24] R. Sazeeleh and R. Rasuli, Some results in local cohomology and serre subcategory, *Romanian Journal of Mathematics and Computer Science*, **3(2) (2013)**, 185-190.
- [25] H. Zoschinger, Minimax Moduln, *J. Algebra*, **102(1986)**, 1-32.
- [26] H. Zoschinger, koalomare Moduln, *Math. Z.*, **170(1980)**, 221-232